

„Associations of birth weight and later life lifestyle factors with risk of cardiovascular disease in the USA” is a article Published in the journal *eClinicalMedicine*.

1. ARTICLE SUMMARY

The study was based on three large, ongoing prospective cohorts:

1. **Health Professionals Follow-up Study (HPFS):** Initiated in 1986, involving 51,529 men.
2. **Nurses' Health Study (NHS):** Initiated in 1976, enrolling 121,700 women.
3. **Nurses' Health Study II (NHS II):** Initiated in 1989, enrolling 116,429 women.

The final analysis included **20,169 men** (12.77%) and **137,730 women** (87.23%). Participants included and excluded from the analysis did not differ significantly in terms of baseline characteristics and the incidence of CVD.

Participants reported birth weight (five categories: <2.5 kg, 2.5–3.15 kg, 3.16–3.82 kg, 3.83–4.5 kg, >4.5 kg) and current data on BMI, smoking, physical activity, and diet every 2–4 years.

In the study, data on height, race, weight, marital status, health status, and other factors were obtained using participants' self-reports. Some of the information was updated every 2-4 years, and during this time participants also reported physical activity and alcohol consumption. A diet quality index based on the DASH diet was created that assessed the participants' diets. Participants were classified into high-risk groups based on lifestyle variables such as BMI, smoking, diet, physical activity, and alcohol consumption. The results of self-reports on weight, physical activity, diet, and smoking were considered reliable based on previous studies in the same group. It was defined as unhealthy based on a BMI of ≥ 25 kg/m², smoking, low physical activity (<30 min/day), poor diet quality (assessed by DASH), and failure to fit into moderate alcohol consumption.

Statistical analysis was based on Cox regression models that included time variables to estimate hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for the association between birth weight categories and cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk. Follow-up periods lasted from the time of completion of the initial questionnaire to the diagnosis of CVD, death, or end of follow-up. Many variables were taken into account, such as age, calendar time, CVD family history, lifestyle, and other health factors. An interaction analysis between low birth weight and unhealthy lifestyle was performed to assess whether their combined effect on CVD risk is greater than the sum of individual effects. A multiplier interaction analysis was used and excess interaction risk (RERI) was calculated. The analysis was performed separately for each of the three cohorts, and then the results were combined in a meta-weight analysis. Sensitivity analyses were also performed, m.in. including data on premature births, parental socioeconomic status, missing data on health factors, as well as other factors such as smoking and maternal medical history. All analyses were conducted using SAS 9.4 software for UNIX systems.

REZULTS

Our study included 20,169 men in HPFS, 52,380 women in NHS, and 85,350 women in NHS II, whose mean (SD) age, at analysis baseline, was 51.69 (9.02), 45.40 (7.12), and 36.00 (4.66) years, respectively. In total, 999 (5.0%) participants in HPFS, 5577 (10.7%) in NHS, and 6707

(7.9%) in NHS II reported a birth weight below 2.5 kg (Table 1). Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics of study participants by birth weight category.

The highest incidence of cardiovascular disease was among participants whose birth weight was less than 2.5 kg in all cohorts (Figure 2). Figure 2 shows crude cumulative incidence of cardiovascular disease according to birthweight category. A: the Health Professionals Follow-up Study (n = 20,169); B: the Nurses' Health Study (n = 52,380); and C: the Nurses' Health Study II (n = 85,350). Similarly, the Cox models showed an increased risk of CVD during adulthood across the categories of decreased birth weight (all P for linear trend – Figure 3)

CHD and stroke were separately evaluated (Table S2 and Table 2)- consistently inverse association between birth weight and CHD risk both in men and women. Low birth weight was also associated with higher stroke risk among women in NHS and NHS II (Table S2), which was not observed among men (Table 2). observed a positive additive interaction between decreasing birth weight and the overall unhealthy score on the risk of CHD among women, but not in men (Table S4 and Table 3). Tables 5 and 6 show each individual lifestyle factor assessed separately the association between birth weight and cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk remained consistent across several sensitivity analyses. These analyses included:

The text explores the relationship between birth weight and the subsequent risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD), specifically coronary heart disease (CHD) and stroke, as well as the interactions with lifestyle factors. The findings from three large prospective cohorts (Health Professionals Follow-up Study, Nurses' Health Study, and Nurses' Health Study II) support the Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD) hypothesis, which suggests that early life stages, including intrauterine development, are critical for the development of chronic diseases later in life.

A lower birth weight is associated with a higher risk of CHD in adulthood, particularly in women. This inverse relationship is not fully explained by lifestyle factors in later life (e.g., physical activity, diet, smoking, alcohol consumption, and BMI).

The study found an additive interaction between decreasing birth weight and unhealthy lifestyle factors (overweight/obesity, smoking, and excessive alcohol intake) on CHD risk, suggesting that low birth weight combined with poor lifestyle choices significantly increases CHD risk.

The association between birth weight and CHD was stronger in women, with an increased risk of CHD when combined with unhealthy lifestyles. In men, however, the relationship was less consistent, and no similar additive interaction was observed.

The study highlights potential sex differences in how prenatal and adult risk factors contribute to the development of CHD, warranting further investigation.

The association between birth weight and stroke risk was less consistent. A significant association was observed in women, but not in men, and only in age-adjusted models. This inconsistency could be due to sample size differences, as fewer men had strokes during the follow-up period in the Health Professionals Follow-up Study (HPFS).

Among women, the interaction between low birth weight and unhealthy lifestyles showed a greater risk of CHD than the sum of each individual risk factor. This suggests that fetal growth restriction (low birth weight) may amplify the adverse effects of poor lifestyle choices, increasing CVD risk.

The mechanisms behind the association between low birth weight and CVD include metabolic alterations in utero, such as insulin resistance and reduced leptin levels, as well as adaptations like endothelial dysfunction and energy allocation toward the development of vital organs. These changes may result in lifelong impacts on cardiovascular health.

Intrauterine factors, such as maternal malnutrition, smoking, and pregnancy complications, might contribute to these metabolic alterations, which predispose individuals to CVD later in life.

The study highlights the long-term impact of birth weight on CVD risk, especially in women, and the synergistic effect of low birth weight combined with unhealthy adult lifestyles. This research underscores the importance of addressing both prenatal conditions and lifestyle factors in preventing cardiovascular diseases.

2. AUTHORS

Yi-Xin Wang- Yi-Xin Wang is a prominent researcher affiliated with the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. His work focuses on environmental health, particularly the impacts of various chemical exposures, such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and haloacetic acids, on human health. His research spans reproductive health, thyroid function, and endocrine disruption, with significant publications in leading journals like *Environmental Science & Technology* and *Environmental International*. Wang collaborates with multidisciplinary teams, exploring epidemiological and biochemical studies to address public health challenges.

H-index: 36 Citations: 4139

Yanping Li- Yanping Li is a prominent researcher and academic specializing in environmental science and public health, with contributions in several areas:

1. **Climate Change and Hydrology:** Dr. Yanping Li, an assistant professor at the University of Saskatchewan and affiliated with the Global Institute for Water Security, focuses on regional climate modeling, boundary layer processes, and the impacts of climate change on precipitation and water resources. Her work aims to advance our understanding of extreme precipitation events and climate adaptation strategies, particularly in regions like the Canadian Prairies
2. **Public Health Research:** Yanping Li has contributed to studies examining dietary patterns, lifestyle factors, and their health impacts. For example, her work at institutions like the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health explores connections between diet, cardiovascular health, and diabetes. These studies highlight critical health trends and preventive measures, with implications for public health policies.

Dr. Li's interdisciplinary research bridges climate science and health, addressing pressing global challenges like climate resilience and sustainable health practices.

H-index: 23 Citations: 1825

Janet W. Rich-Edwards- Janet W. Rich-Edwards is a distinguished epidemiologist and associate professor at Harvard Medical School and the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. She also serves as the Director of Lifecourse Epidemiology at Brigham and Women's Hospital. Her research focuses on how early-life experiences, particularly childhood trauma

and pregnancy complications, influence long-term health outcomes, such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes. She employs interdisciplinary approaches, including leveraging large datasets and integrating machine learning, to advance the understanding of these connections.

H-index: 124 Citations: 55759

Andrea A. Florio- Andrea A. Florio is a researcher with expertise in public health and epidemiology. He is associated with the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, where he contributes to studies focused on chronic diseases, cancer epidemiology, and metabolic health. His academic work often involves interdisciplinary approaches, utilizing both large-scale population data and advanced statistical methods to understand the underlying factors influencing health outcomes. Florio has collaborated on several high-impact publications that delve into topics like the biological mechanisms of chronic illnesses and the effectiveness of public health interventions.

For more details about his contributions, his academic profile is accessible through platforms such as Frontiers Loop or research publication databases like PubMed.

H-index: 15 Citations: 1461

Zhilei Shan- Dr. Zhilei Shan, M.D., Ph.D., is a postdoctoral research fellow in the Department of Nutrition at the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. His research primarily focuses on the intersection of dietary patterns, nutrition, and chronic disease outcomes. He has contributed to several high-impact studies analyzing diet quality and health outcomes, including the effects of low-carbohydrate and low-fat diets on mortality. His work often emphasizes the importance of diet quality rather than just macronutrient composition, advocating for improvements in food choices to promote better public health.

Dr. Shan has collaborated with leading institutions, including Tongji Medical College at Huazhong University of Science and Technology in Wuhan, China. His studies have also explored trends in macronutrient consumption and their associations with public health, providing insights into reducing disease risks through dietary interventions.

H-index: 36 Citations: 7914

Siwen Wang- is a physician-scientist at the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, specializing in the intersection of nutrition, mental health, and chronic disease outcomes. Her research focuses on identifying modifiable lifestyle factors that influence long-term health conditions, particularly post-viral syndromes like long COVID.

Dr. Wang has contributed to studies exploring how psychological factors, such as stress, anxiety, and depression, prior to COVID-19 infection, may increase the risk of developing long COVID. Her findings suggest that addressing mental health alongside physical health is crucial for both prevention and treatment strategies. She also investigates the role of healthy lifestyle habits, including diet, exercise, and mental well-being, in mitigating chronic conditions and enhancing public health resilience.

H-index: 16 Citations: 1864

JoAnn E. Manson- is a renowned endocrinologist and epidemiologist, currently serving as the Chief of the Division of Preventive Medicine at Brigham and Women's Hospital and a Professor of Medicine at Harvard Medical School. She is also a Professor in the Department of Epidemiology at the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. Her research focuses on the prevention of chronic diseases, including heart disease, diabetes, and cancer, through randomized clinical trials examining nutritional and lifestyle factors as well as the role of hormones in disease development.

Dr. Manson has played a pivotal role in several landmark studies, such as the Women's Health Initiative, the Nurses' Health Study, and the VITamin D and OmegA-3 Trial (VITAL). Her work has significantly contributed to understanding women's health, cardiovascular disease, and the effects of supplements like vitamin D and omega-3 fatty acids.

H-index: 91 Citations: 29525

Kenneth J. Mukamal- is an accomplished physician and researcher, serving as the Associate Section Chief for Research in General Medicine at Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center (BIDMC) and holding an academic appointment at Harvard Medical School. His research primarily focuses on the role of dietary and lifestyle factors, particularly alcohol consumption, in influencing cardiovascular and neurocognitive health. He has explored diverse topics, including novel cardiovascular risk factors, diabetes in older adults, and the effects of non-esterified fatty acids on cardiometabolic health.

H-index: 106 Citations: 45069

Eric B. Rimm- is a prominent nutrition scientist and epidemiologist who serves as a Professor of Epidemiology and Nutrition at the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health and a Professor of Medicine at Harvard Medical School. He is the Director of the Program in Cardiovascular Epidemiology at Harvard, focusing on the relationship between dietary and lifestyle factors and the risk of chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, obesity, and diabetes.

Dr. Rimm has been instrumental in advancing public health interventions, particularly in designing programs targeting dietary improvements for children and underserved populations. He has contributed extensively to research, with over 400 peer-reviewed publications. His work includes leadership roles in significant studies such as the Health Professionals Follow-Up Study, a long-term investigation involving 50,000 male health professionals.

H-index: 255 Citations: 321825

Jorge E. Chavarro- is a prominent professor of Nutrition and Epidemiology at the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. His research primarily explores the intersection of nutrition, lifestyle, and metabolic factors with human reproduction and fertility. This includes studying how these elements influence reproductive milestones and broader health outcomes, such as pregnancy complications and developmental origins of health and disease.

Dr. Chavarro is involved in significant cohort studies, including leading the Nurses' Health Study 3, which tracks over 50,000 women, and overseeing the nutritional components of the EARTH Study, focusing on couples undergoing infertility treatment. He also participates in

global research through the Young Men's Studies consortium, investigating environmental impacts on testicular function across Denmark, Spain, and the United States.

H-index: 91 Citations: 29525

3. Journal

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